

RAPID RESOLUTION OF A SEVERE MULTIFACTORIAL PERI-IMPLANT OSTEONECROTIC LESION IN A MEDICALLY COMPROMISED PATIENT TREATED WITH A METRONIDAZOLE-RELEASING HYDROGEL SCAFFOLD (AEVIZOL): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Severe peri-implant osteonecrotic lesions in oncologic and medically compromised patients may result from the convergence of multiple local and systemic factors, including peri-implant infection, repeated oral surgery, smoking, cardiovascular disease, chemotherapy, and previous radiotherapy. Local drug-delivery hydrogels may offer potential advantages in contaminated and poorly vascularized sites. **Case Presentation:** A 67-year-old man with a history of multiple malignancies, numerous surgical procedures, three myocardial infarctions, active oncologic treatment in 2024, smoking, and complex long-term polypharmacotherapy had undergone original bimaxillary All-on-4 rehabilitation in 2011 using Nobel Speedy implants and long-term reinforced provisional prostheses. In 2025, after rapid necrotizing peri-implant breakdown in the left posterior mandible, a second severe osteonecrotic-infective lesion developed in the anterior mandible following placement of a new implant in the 3.1/3.2 area. On 10/11/2025 the implant was removed.

Intraoperatively, the bone appeared grayish, frankly necrotic, friable on curettage, and associated with abundant dense purulent exudate. After careful surgical curettage, the cavity was completely filled with AEVIZOL, a patented hydrogel scaffold with slow metronidazole release. In the AEVIZOL system, metronidazole is preliminarily micronized to below 10 μm using air-nitrogen jet technology in order to prevent overheating and possible deterioration; this process improves its solubility, bioavailability, and affinity for the hydrogel matrix, whose aqueous component is predominant. The site was then sutured with silk. At 15 days, the soft tissues showed favorable trophic recovery. CBCT performed on 13/02/2026 demonstrated substantial healing of the site, allowing reimplantation on 24/03/2026. At re-entry, the bone appeared clinically trophic and compact. **Conclusions:** In this medically compromised patient with a probable multifactorial peri-implant osteonecrotic lesion, local treatment with AEVIZOL was associated with rapid soft-tissue healing and early radiographic bone recovery sufficient to allow reimplantation after approximately 3.5 months. Further studies are required to clarify the role of metronidazole-releasing hydrogels in high-risk clinical settings.

KEYWORDS: Dental Implants; Osteonecrosis; Peri-Implantitis; Metronidazole; Hydrogels; Drug Delivery Systems; All-on-4; Nobel Biocare Speedy implants; Peri-implant infection.

INTRODUCTION

The biological management of severe peri-implant infective-necrotic lesions remains a challenge, particularly in medically compromised patients. Peri-implant inflammatory breakdown may be accelerated by smoking, systemic comorbidities, impaired vascular supply, oncologic therapies, repeated surgical trauma, and prosthetic overload. In oncologic settings, osteonecrosis of the jaws is increasingly regarded as a multifactorial condition in which local infection, bone manipulation, pharmacologic exposure, radiotherapy, and host-related factors may converge.

Local metronidazole-based delivery systems have been investigated in periodontology, peri-implantology, post-extraction alveolitis, and oral drug delivery. Hydrogel scaffolds may offer several theoretical advantages, including high local drug concentration, reduced systemic exposure, controlled release, adaptation to irregular cavities, and persistence in moist environments. Recent literature on hydrogel-based systems includes films, gels, injectable formulations, thermosensitive matrices, and hydrophilic PVA-based or conceptually similar scaffolds for periodontal use.

The present case is reported because of:^[1] the patient's markedly compromised systemic condition;^[2] the unusually aggressive presentation of the peri-implant necrotic-infective lesion;^[3] the use of an Italian patented hydrogel scaffold (AEVIZOL) with slow metronidazole release; and^[4] the rapid clinical and radiographic recovery that made new implant placement possible within a relatively short time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Clinical framework of the case

This retrospective case report is based on chronological reconstruction of the clinical chart, panoramic radiographic documentation, follow-up CBCT imaging, and intraoral photographic documentation of soft-tissue healing. Its aim is to describe the local management of a severe peri-implant osteonecrotic lesion of likely multifactorial origin in an oncologic patient with severe cardiovascular disease and a high systemic risk profile.

Material used: AEVIZOL

AEVIZOL is an innovative hydrogel covered by Italian Patent No. 0001417592. According to the technical and patent information provided, it consists of a three-dimensional hydrogel scaffold whose main component is water, with 2% polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The preparation includes final cross-linking of the system and incorporation of hydrophilic metronidazole, allowing the material to function as an ancillary drug delivery system. The function of the AEVIZOL hydrogel is to carry and provide a controlled, continuous release of metronidazole over time. This release amounts to 1.2 mg per day, representing a local delivery approximately 2,000 times lower than the equivalent systemic dose.

Before being added to the hydrogel, metronidazole undergoes a specific processing step: it is micronized to below 10 µm using an air-nitrogen jet mill in order to prevent molecular overheating and possible deterioration. According to the manufacturer's technical information, this procedure significantly improves the drug's solubility and bioavailability. The antibiotic processed in this way also shows greater affinity for the hydrogel, in keeping with the predominantly aqueous nature of the matrix.

A clinically relevant feature is that, unlike many other local gels, the material does not require prior drying of the pocket or cavity before application. In the present case, AEVIZOL was used to completely fill the bony defect after surgical curettage, with the aim of locally

stabilizing the clot, preserving volume, supporting hemostasis, and promoting prolonged metronidazole release.

Observed outcomes

- [1] The outcomes considered in this report were:
- [2] the clinical course of the soft tissues during early healing;
- [3] control of local infection and symptoms;
- [4] radiographic evolution of the treated site;
- [5] the possibility of surgical re-entry and reimplantation;
- [6] and the clinical quality of bone at re-entry.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 67-year-old male patient was referred to our clinic for management of complications related to a long-standing bimaxillary implant-prosthetic rehabilitation. In 2011, he had been treated in our office with the original bimaxillary All-on-4 protocol using Nobel Biocare Speedy Groovy implants. In accordance with the protocol, straight multi-unit abutments were placed on the anterior implants, whereas 30° angled multi-unit abutments were placed on the posterior implants, both in the maxilla and in the mandible. Because the patient did not have the financial resources required for definitive prostheses, he continued for years to function with provisional prostheses, suitably modified by adding molars and reinforced with CAD-designed fiberglass mesostructures.

Medical history

The systemic condition was markedly compromised. The medical history included severe trauma to one lower limb, followed by numerous surgical procedures; repeated surgery for disseminated malignancies involving the bladder, kidney, prostate, and stomach; and three myocardial infarctions. From 2016 onward, the patient underwent eight surgical procedures for malignancies and recurrences, one course of radiotherapy, and more than ten cycles of chemotherapy, the last three involving experimental drugs. The most recent chart entries also reported renal disease, severe ischemic heart disease, smoking of approximately 10 cigarettes per day, and ongoing oncologic follow-up. Chronic pharmacologic treatment recorded in 2026 included bisoprolol, ramipril, omeprazole/pariet, low-dose aspirin, spironolactone, lipid-lowering therapy, Carvasin, ranolazine, clopidogrel, and additional cardiovascular medications.

Long-term implant history

From 2011 to 2024, the clinical diary documented long-term functional survival of the full-arch implant-supported prostheses, despite multiple maintenance procedures, including fractures or detachment of prosthetic teeth, reinforcement procedures, repairs, and periodic occlusal adjustments, all fully consistent with the nature of reinforced provisional restorations. Despite these events, the original rehabilitation showed remarkable long-term clinical durability, especially considering the prolonged use of provisional prosthetic structures.

First necrotizing event: posterior mandible

After years of tissue health and clinical stability, radiographic and clinical examination in September 2025 revealed diffuse peri-implantitis, with a particularly severe condition affecting the distal implant in the left posterior mandible at site 35. According to the clinical interpretation, this site had developed rapidly progressive necrotizing peri-implantitis with rapid global loss of implant-bone contact, likely favored by the oncologic background and previous systemic therapies. On 09/10/2025 the compromised implant was removed, new mandibular implants were inserted, and the pre-existing prosthesis was modified for immediate loading in order to preserve occlusal stability. Site 35 was also treated locally with AEVIZOL, with subsequent complete ossification demonstrable both clinically at surgical re-entry and radiographically on cone beam computed tomography.

Index event: severe anterior mandibular osteonecrotic-infective lesion

The focus of the present case report, however, is the subsequent lesion that developed in the anterior mandible, in the intermediate region between teeth 41 and 42, after placement of a new implant on 09/10/2025. Approximately one month later, on 10/11/2025, the patient returned with swelling and pain. Clinical and radiographic evaluation led to the diagnosis of a severe peri-implant osteonecrotic-infective lesion. The implant was therefore removed immediately.

Intraoperatively, the bone appeared grayish and frankly necrotic, with abundant dense purulent exudate. During curettage with a Molt 2/4 curette, the necrotic bone was friable, exfoliating, and crumbling. After careful debridement and cleansing of the site, the entire cavity was flooded with AEVIZOL.

After placement and in situ cross-linking, the material showed good volumetric stability and satisfactory local hemostasis. The site was sutured with silk.

Early healing phase

Clinical photographs taken on 25/11/2025, approximately 15 days after implant removal and the first AEVIZOL treatment, showed favorable soft-tissue conditions at the time of suture removal (Figs. 8-10). The peri-lesional mucosa appeared globally trophic, with no evident active suppuration and satisfactory stability of the treated site profile. A residual whitish material was still visible within the surgical site, compatible with persistence of the locally placed material and/or ongoing tissue reorganization. In other views, the silk sutures were still visible in place.

Radiographic follow-up and reimplantation

The radiographic sequence is particularly relevant in this case. Baseline panoramic radiographs documented the original bimaxillary All-on-4 setup in 2011 (Fig. 1). Follow-up panoramic radiographs over the years confirmed the continued presence of the long-term full-arch provisional prostheses and, later, the progressive worsening of the mandibular condition in 2025 (Fig. 2). The panoramic radiograph taken on 16/09/2025 (Fig. 3) showed advanced peri-implant breakdown in the mandible, especially in the left posterior sector, where the tilted implant at site 35 displayed massive sleeve-like bone loss along its entire implant surface. The post-surgical panoramic radiograph of 09/10/2025 documented removal of the compromised implants and insertion of new mandibular implants (Fig. 4). The panoramic follow-up obtained on 09/01/2026 showed the condition after management of the anterior mandibular complication (Fig. 5).

The most important finding, however, emerged from cone beam computed tomography performed on 13/02/2026 (Fig. 7), which documented substantial recovery at site 41/42 and supported the feasibility of reimplantation. On 24/03/2026, approximately three and a half months after removal of the implant associated with the necrotic lesion and the first AEVIZOL treatment, the site was reopened and a new implant was inserted. Intraoperatively, the bone was described as trophic, compact, and of good consistency, clinically compatible with type N density according to the histomorphometric bone-density classification proposed by Rao W. and Trisi P.^[26] The post-loading panoramic radiograph confirmed implant repositioning (Fig. 6), and subsequent clinical controls were uneventful.

DISCUSSION

This case is noteworthy because it combines long-term implant function, sudden biological destabilization, severe systemic compromise, and unexpectedly rapid local recovery after treatment of a severe osteonecrotic-infective lesion.

Multifactorial pathogenesis

The lesion should be interpreted as likely multifactorial rather than attributed to a single cause. Several converging factors may have contributed, including severe oncologic history, chemotherapy and radiotherapy in 2024, repeated surgical procedures, smoking, cardiovascular compromise, reduced vascular reserve, chronic peri-implant inflammation, multiple implant and prosthetic reinterventions, and a plausibly impaired host biological response. The literature on implant-related osteonecrosis in oncologic or medically compromised patients shows that these lesions may occur months or years after implant placement and may be promoted or amplified by peri-implant infection, surgery, pharmacologic exposure, prosthetic factors, and systemic burden.^[13-21]

Although the available documentation does not clearly demonstrate treatment with antiresorptive or antiangiogenic agents, the literature nevertheless supports the broader concept that peri-implant osteonecrotic lesions in oncologic patients are often biologically complex and arise from the interaction of multiple local and systemic stressors.^[13-21] Therefore, the definition of a multifactorial peri-implant osteonecrotic lesion appears methodologically sound and appropriately cautious.

Rationale for local hydrogel therapy

Metronidazole has a long-standing role in dentistry because of its activity against obligate anaerobes and its use in periodontal and odontogenic infections.^[1] More recent studies suggest that local metronidazole-based systems may also offer anti-inflammatory benefits or biofilm modulation in selected oral environments.^[2-12] Clinical and translational studies have investigated metronidazole in gels, films, thermosensitive systems, and injectable hydrogels for periodontitis, peri-implant disease, post-extraction alveolitis, and buccal drug delivery.^[3-12,22-25]

Hydrogel carriers offer several properties that may be advantageous in infected oral defects: adaptation to irregular cavities, persistence in moist environments, potential for controlled release, and reduction of systemic drug burden.^[3-12,22-25] Many published formulations,

although not identical to AEVIZOL, share conceptually similar features, including hydrophilic polymer matrices, three-dimensional scaffold behavior, antibiotic loading, and suitability for local delivery in moist periodontal or peri-implant environments.^[4-10,22-25] Particularly relevant are PVA-containing or PVA-based systems, which more closely approximate the conceptual design of AEVIZOL.^[22,25]

Clinical relevance of the case

The intraoperative scenario on 10/11/2025 was severe: grayish necrotic bone, dense purulent exudate, and friable tissue collapsing during curettage. In such a biologically hostile environment, the observed outcome was clinically unexpected. Within 15 days, the soft tissues showed favorable recovery; within approximately 3 months, cone beam computed tomography findings supported reimplantation; and at re-entry the bone appeared clinically trophic and compact. Although causality cannot be inferred from a single case, these findings support the hypothesis that AEVIZOL may have contributed not only as a metronidazole carrier, but also as a local scaffold capable of promoting site stability, hemostasis, and tissue recovery.

Differential interpretation and limitations

This case report does not demonstrate superiority over other treatments, nor does it allow one to establish to what extent the favorable outcome was attributable to surgical curettage, infection control, hydrogel persistence, reduction in bacterial load, host biological recovery, or a synergistic combination of these factors. The absence of histologic analysis is an important limitation, and the precise etiologic weight of previous oncologic therapies remains inferential. Moreover, because no indexed journal publications specifically addressing AEVIZOL in dentistry were identified in the currently available literature, discussion of the product must remain cautious and based on patent and technical information, as well as on analogy with the broader hydrogel literature.^[22-25]

Nevertheless, the strength of the present case lies in the consistency among the clinical chronology, photographic evolution of the soft tissues, and radiographic and cone beam computed tomography recovery, which ultimately made reimplantation possible within a timeframe that was highly favorable in relation to the severity of the original lesion in a patient who was already at high systemic risk.

CONCLUSION

In this case report, an oncologic and medically compromised patient carrying a long-standing bimaxillary implant-prosthetic rehabilitation developed a severe peri-implant osteonecrotic-infective lesion in the anterior mandible after reimplantation. Following implant removal, surgical debridement, and local application of the metronidazole-releasing hydrogel scaffold AEVIZOL, early soft-tissue recovery and rapid radiographic bone healing were observed, allowing a new implant to be placed after approximately 3.5 months. Within the limitations of a single case, AEVIZOL appears to be a promising local adjunct in the management of severe multifactorial peri-implant necrotic lesions in high-risk patients.

Figures and Legends

Figure 1: Baseline panoramic radiograph (2011) showing the original bimaxillary All-on-4 rehabilitation.

Figure 2. Panoramic radiograph obtained in 2020 documenting long-term maintenance of the full-arch implant-supported provisional prostheses.

Figura 3. Panoramic radiograph dated 16/09/2025 showing advanced mandibular peri-implant breakdown, particularly in the left posterior sector (Q3).

Figura 4. Post-surgical panoramic radiograph dated 09/10/2025 after removal of compromised implants and insertion of new mandibular implants.

Figura 5. Follow-up panoramic radiograph dated 09/01/2026 after management of the anterior mandibular complication.

Figura 6. Panoramic radiograph obtained in 2026 documenting the condition after site recovery and reimplantation.

Figura 7. Cone beam computed tomography image dated 13/02/2026 showing recovery of the anterior mandibular site and feasibility of reimplantation.

Figura 8. Clinical photograph taken on 25/11/2025, 15 days after implant removal and the first AEVIZOL application, showing generally favorable soft-tissue conditions.

Figura 9. Full clinical view of the lower arch at the 25/11/2025 follow-up during suture removal.

Figura 10. Close-up clinical view of the treated anterior mandibular site at the 25/11/2025 follow-up.

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